

STUDYING SOCIAL PROBLEMS AFFECTING EXPERT YOUTH UNEMPLOYMENT IN KAZAKHSTAN LABOR MARKET

ESTUDIO DE PROBLEMAS SOCIALES QUE AFECTAN EL DESEMPLEO DE JÓVENES EXPERTOS EN KAZAJSTÁN

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RESUMEN

Esta investigación tiene como objetivo investigar los problemas sociales que afectan el desempleo de jóvenes expertos en el mercado laboral de Kazajstán. Los datos de investigación se recopilaban a través de un cuestionario. Los resultados de la investigación mostraron que, para Kazajstán, el problema del desempleo entre los jóvenes es muy grave. La proporción de jóvenes desempleados es la octava parte de la población activa total. El mayor problema entre los jóvenes expertos desempleados es que los empleadores son reacios a contratar a jóvenes sin experiencia laboral, y en este momento la mayoría de los jóvenes no son capaces de crear un negocio como una empresa familiar.

Palabras clave: mercado laboral, sociedad moderna, autoempleo, desempleo de jóvenes expertos.

ABSTRACT

This research is aimed at investigating the social problems affecting the unemployment of young experts in the labor market of Kazakhstan. Research data were collected through a questionnaire, which included open-answer questions and closed-answer questions. The results of research showed that for Kazakhstan, the problem of unemployment among young people is very acute. The unemployed youth ratio is eighth of the total active population. The biggest problem among unemployed young experts is that employers are reluctant to hire young people without a job experience, and at the moment most of the young people are not capable of creating a business as a family business.

Keywords: labor market, modern society, self-employment, expert youth unemployment.

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INTRODUCTION

The article is devoted to one of the urgent problems of modern Kazakhstan society - youth unemployment. The youth unemployment is one of the most pressing problems in the world. Especially often it occurs in the countries moving from one social system to another (from the former socialist to the modern market), to which Kazakhstan belongs. During the transition to a market economy, the new sovereign states formed as a result of the collapse of the USSR faced many adaptation difficulties, which include the problems of employment and unemployment. The shortcomings of the market and financial infrastructures have led to a lack of economic and financial mechanisms that affect the production development, which has led to the emergence of social phenomena such as poverty and unemployment in some areas. Youth unemployment has its own specifics: the individuals at a young age tend to have a lower level of skills or less experience, and therefore have very low chances for integration in the labor market.

Unemployment is one of the most basic and important socio-economic problems, especially worsening during the economic crisis. An unemployed individual, devoid of professional identity and material income, faces various social and economic problems. At present, a complex and highly contradictory process of economic transformation continues to be implemented in Kazakhstan, within which the in-depth transformations take place in the system of employment relations. The main direction of this process is the formation of the labor market, which can fundamentally change the entire system of employment relations.

As the least experienced and unprotected category of the population, during the economic stagnation, recessions, crises, young people are more affected by their consequences and it is more difficult for them to integrate into the labor market. As noted in the report of the International Labor Organization (2014), about 74.5 million young people aged 15 to 24 years old were registered as unemployed in 2013, which is almost 1 million more than in 2012 (Committee of Statistics of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 2017). Despite the efforts of all states, youth unemployment (in the world) has been 13,1% on average, that is, 3 times more than the unemployment rate among other categories of the population (Committee of Statistics of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 2017).

The topic relevance is explained by the fact that, firstly, young people constitute the largest part of the capable population of Kazakhstan, and secondly, young people now determine the political, economic and social structure of society (Social and Economic Development of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 2017). In addition, young people are the most vulnerable group in the labor market. Despite the urgency of this problem, it receives very little attention in the scientific papers, in the media and in the government documents.

A number of problems arise for graduates after graduation. One of the main ones is the choice of the future profession. The problem of the formation of professional identity is particularly relevant at the present time both from a practical and scientific standpoint. It should be noted that the modern sociological science has paid considerable attention to this important problem. The basis of the theoretical study of employment problems and the labor market was laid by the representatives of the classical employment theory: A. Smith, D. Ricardo, Mil, J. Keynes, P. Samuelson, F. Hayek and other researchers. T. Parsons and N. Smelser (2006) developed the theory of economic action as a kind of social one objectively conditioned by society. Thus, according to Parsons, provision with the decent work is the basis of social protection of the population, development of the human resource potential and an important condition for the implementation, the main way to improve the quality of life and to increase the social wealth (Parsons, 1968).

An appeal to the problem theory shows that the study of unemployment among young specialists was carried out by: Ganskau E.Yu., Ponomarenko T.I., Geleta V.I., Akulich M.M., Zaslavskaya T.I., Savinova A.N., Borisova A.A., Kuzmin S.A., Maslova I.S., Vidyapin V.I., Zhuravleva G.P. (Yelzhanova, Zhumatay, and Sarzhanizy, 2015).

The problems of socialization and employment of Kazakhstan youth are being considered in the papers of Kazakstan scientists. For example, M.S. Azhenov, Z.K. Shaukenov and others (Abdiraymova & Serikzhanova, 2013) analyze the methodological and empirical aspects of the youth problems, its role and place in the social structure of modern society.

The youth topic was touched upon in the papers of such Kazakhstan sociologists as: G. Gabdullina, N. Namysbaeva, J. Ledneva, T. Kaldybaeva, G. Telebaev, A. Shakenov. To the special features of the ethnocultural socialization of youth are devoted the papers of K. Zharikbayev, Zh. Nauryzbay, S. Kaliyev, K. Kozhakhmetova, S. Uzakbaeva (Yelzhanova, Zhumatay, & Sarzhanizy, 2015).

One of the main directions of the strategy of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan "Kazakhstan-2050" is to increase the profitability and socio-economic stability of Kazakhstanis. It is envisaged that the fight against unemployment in a specific sector of the economy can be solved by creating new jobs, active employment policies and planning unemployment insurance.

According to the above mentioned statements, main purpose of the current research was to investigate the social problems affecting the unemployment of young experts in the Kazakhstani labor market. In order to achieve this goal, we first began studying the theoretical bases and literature of unemployment in

Kazakhstan, and then we gathered information about the obstacles and problems of youth employment with the help of the questionnaire.

METHODS

The sociological research was conducted by the questioning method together with the information-analytical center Korkyt Ata Kyzylorda State University (N = 400 graduates) in 2016, which made it possible to clarify the features of vocational and labor indicators of the university graduates. The questionnaire covers open and closed questions on the issue under study. The respondent answered open questions freely without anyone's interference, on closed questions they chose an opinion based on the answers of the specialists.

Study object: youth of Kyzylorda at the age from 15 to 29 years old, covering various fields of society. The study included a quota method to form the sampling population by age, sex, and socio-occupational feature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The own characteristics of the labor market in the regions of Kazakhstan are determined by several factors. The conjuncture of jobs in the regional labor market is limited due to the low population density and the narrowly specialized nature of the agricultural sector. As a result, the discrepancy between supply and demand for labor is complicated, the coverage of the use of labor resources and its effectiveness is significantly reduced, and the constitutional rights to work of rural residents are limited. The structure of the regional employment field, in comparison with other fields of employment during formation, depends on natural climatic and seasonal circumstances.

The uneven distribution of people in rural areas, the development level of rural areas and the difference in the production specialization creates an uneven distribution of labor resources, which determines the following features of the labor market:

Firstly, many rural workers themselves are both owners and the main labor force. Only such freedom fixes the interaction of the landowner with the land and justifies the present agrarian relationships. Taking into account the peculiarities of specific lands makes it possible to fulfill the desires of people to have agriculture, to satisfy the society's need for their own products.

Secondly, the decline in the financial and economic situation of agricultural production and construction does not provide an opportunity to finance the non-productive sectors of the region and increase production. The quality of social services in rural areas and their decrease in volume is based on the development of social infrastructure and leads to a reduction in the labor potential of the region.

As a result, the demand for labor in the production and non-production sectors is declining.

Thirdly, the balance between the shrinking jobs in the region and the supply of an increasing workforce is lost. An increase in the labor supply was due to the decline in production and in introduction of new jobs, the job elimination reduced the need for labor.

Fourthly, the emergence of hidden unemployment, in addition to open, which is characterized by the complexity of determining its scope, as well as regulation by the state structures.

Fifthly, the university graduates, as a part of young people with a high educational and professional level, are particularly closely interrelated with modern trends and contradictory changes in the society. In turn, their contribution to the development of the country's economy depends on their attitude to work, because they will form the bulk of the employed population and will determine the pace of its development soon.

In Kazakhstan, the determination of the status of a young specialist is underway: "To date, a young specialist, who is a graduate of a higher educational institution and who has been working by specialty for three years is considered a young specialist". "At the present stage, personal competitiveness is becoming a key moment in the relationship between the state and the youth," said Madiyar Kozhahmet, the Head of the Department of Youth Policy of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan, in an interview for the website Pm (Skuryatipa, 2002).

The big changes that took place in the country that switched to the market relations influenced the employment issues and working order. They include the issue with the newly graduated, which remain difficult. It is so, because it is more profitable for the employers to hire experienced workers with work experience. It is important to note that 65.4% of graduates want to work by their specialty. According to the study, 5.7% have not still decided on the choice of work by the specialty. We can also note the high level of professionally oriented strategies of Kazakhstan graduates.

When revealing the reasons for the unwillingness to work by the specialty, it was found that the prevailing reasons was a lack of practical knowledge, a lack of work experience (33.3%), low-paid work by the specialty (26.7%) for young men. The reasons for unwillingness to work by the specialty are somewhat different for women: impossibility to get a job by the specialty (36.4%) and a lack of interest in their specialty (27.3%). (See Table 1).

Table 1. Reasons for Disinclination for Work Within Specialty

Young Men	
lack of practical knowledge, lack of work experience	33,3%
work in specialty is under-paid	26,7%
Young Girls	
in-unemployment in specialty	36,4%
lack of support in specialty	27,3%

According to the survey results, in order to determine "Employment opportunities after graduation", the option "Using employment services" was noted by 39.5. "By competition, announcement, with the help of parents, relatives and friends" - 35.5%, "I do not know how" - 6.9%, "I count on luck, chance, I rely only on myself" - 18.1%. (See Diagram 1)

Diagram 1. Employment Opportunities After Graduation

According to the statistics of the Employment Center, 1.5 thousand people apply to the employment services. Most of the unemployed people, coming from the target groups aged 16 to 28 years old, who applied to the employment centers, are urban unemployed - 944 people or 64.5 percent, respectively, rural unemployed amount to 526 people or 35.5 percent, respectively. Of the total number of youth applying

to the employment centers, 24.1 percent or 357 people were employed through the intermediary of employment agencies, among them - 246 people or 68.9 percent are urban people and 111 or 31.1 percent - rural people.

According to the survey results "Assess your ability to work", in order to determine how young people characterize their future, the majority of respondents - 88% - answered that they were confident in their labor professional abilities, and only 5% expressed uncertainty about their abilities.

It turned out that the employment issue is also among the most pressing problems facing the youth of Kyzylorda. Most respondents noted that, unfortunately, the distribution system of the university graduates was abolished (30.9%). Every fourth respondent believes that the country's economy is in a "stagnant" state and career counseling is poorly posed. Accordingly, the number of those who say that the quality of education in the universities is low does not meet the economy requirements - 23%. (See Table 2)

Table 2. Why do you think that it is difficult to be employed presently?

Because the existed system of distribution of the University graduates was abolished	30,9%
Because the country's economy is in a "stagnant" state	20,7%
Because the majority of enterprises closed down its operations	15,2%
Because of poor career guidance	14,6%
Because the quality of education in universities is low, it does not meet the requirements of the economy	10,3%
Be neutral	8,3

We also made an analysis of the gender's impact on the prospective nature of employment by the specialty. There were no significant differences in this indicator in terms of employment, which can be explained approximately by the same conditions that young people face in the labor market (see Diagram 2).

Diagram 2. The gender's impact on the prospective nature of employment by the specialty

When analyzing the data, it has turned out that most graduates are not sure about their employment by the specialty after graduation. Only about one in ten graduates believe that it will be easy.

When answering the question "What, in your opinion, does prevent the young specialist from finding job?" 24% of respondents indicated a lack of a permanent place of work and some difficulties in finding job, 11% of respondents consider the issue of the danger of losing their jobs to be topical, 23% noted the high cost of food and utilities, 10% of respondents indicated a shortage of money for quality treatment, 32% considered their earnings low.

The problem of rural youth migration to cities remains acute. According to statistics, the number of young people who moved from the villages to the city increased 2.5 times compared to the last year. In 2014, the share of young people was 41.4% out of the total number of people, who made internal relocation. Of course, the main reason for the mass migration of young people to the city is study and job search.

At the same time, the survey revealed the readiness and the desire of graduates to work in the countryside. 46.2% of graduates are ready to go and work in the countryside immediately after graduation, which is connected, first of all, with the availability of jobs in the countryside. In this regard, the share of young people from the total number of rural residents remains at a high level. In 2015, the number of

rural residents was 29.8% (Fursova, Shakirova, Nikitina, Spirchagova, & Machpal Syzdykova, 2017).

When identifying the arguments for working in the village of a young specialist, we identified the most significant ones: it is very important to be provided with housing (29.9%), to have the opportunity for career growth (22.4%), as well as to be able to work by the specialty (15.4%). The possibility of housing provision was the most significant factor and indicated that the graduates appreciated the importance of having their own housing as the main life resource. (See Table 3)

Table 3. What, in your opinion, can affect a desire of a young specialist to work in the countryside?

Payment of sign-on bonus	17,2%
Fringe benefits	15,1%
Accomodation services	29,9%
Career prospects	22,4%
Opportunity to work in specialty	15,4%

The unemployment is one of the most pressing problems in the world. And it often occurs in the countries with transitional economies. For example, such a process is currently taking place in Kazakhstan. It brings other new problems with itself, for example, the growth of shadow economy - wage payment "in envelopes", that is, without tax payment, which is especially acute for the visitors from neighboring economically undeveloped republics for the employment purpose. Therefore, many politicians pay great attention to the unemployment problem in their election programs prior to elections to local government bodies (Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Population of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 2017).

CONCLUSION

For Kazakhstan, the unemployment problem among young people is very acute: the proportion of unemployed youth is one-eighth of the total active population.

As the research result, we identified several reasons: level of economic development, social situation of the population, inflation, inadequate number of workplaces, or high requirements for hiring, as well as an employment contract can lead to job loss.

Currently, there are many graduated unemployed young people, which is due to

the fact that the employer does not accept them without work experience. Hence, there are ways of finding a job, where you cannot do without family ties.

According to the Statistics Agency of the Republic of Kazakhstan for the Kyzylorda Region, in the 3rd quarter of 2015 the overall unemployment rate was 5.0% (2014 - 5.2%), the youth unemployment rate: 15-24 years old - 5.9% (in 2014 - 6.7%), 15-28 years old - 4.7% (2014 - 6.7%), and decreased from 0.7 to 0.2% compared with the same period of the last year, respectively (Fursova et al., 2017). It is common knowledge that unemployed people in Kazakhstan mean only those citizens who are registered at the employment center in the relevant status. A significant proportion of citizens, who do not have formal employment and receive income in kind, are included in the statistics as self-employed. The foregoing suggests that the real level of youth unemployment is well above 5%.

Thus, the peculiarities of the value preferences of Kazakhstan graduates are oriented toward achieving personal goals. In other words, the strategies of Kazakhstan graduates are not oriented to the slogan of "wild capitalism" - "money at any price", but they correspond to the principles of civilized market relations. On the one hand, the statist, paternalistic tradition, reliance on state aid, remain in the youth environment. On the other hand, the graduates of Kazakhstan form their social and economic strategy, relying on the market values. At the same time, the preservation of traditionalism in the instrumental values predetermines the need to increase the personal potential of graduates, to develop and implement programs aimed at increasing their competitiveness in the labor market and professional services designed to form the most effective, successful socio-economic strategies. This hybridity is manifested as a result of accumulation in the life strategies of young people of various behavioral patterns as a result of inheritance by the young generation of the value-regulatory and ideological structures that are successively linked to the previous social and historical conditions and new ones that correspond to the contemporary life realities.

According to the research results, the unemployed youth includes two main most vulnerable groups of young people, who have the greatest problems in the labor market:

- youth with a low level of labor integration. This group of citizens has formal education, however, a low level of qualification or an incorrect choice of a profession does not allow them finding a job even during the period of economic growth;
- young people who have not completed training in the educational institutions. These young people usually come from families of labor migrants, rural residents or representatives of vulnerable groups of the population.

SUMMARY

At present, a large-scale employment program is being implemented in Kazakhstan - the Employment Road Map-2020, - which contains advanced employment mechanisms: retraining, advanced training, youth practice, direct job creation. All issues were touched upon in these programs. They include social work places and youth practice, vocational training and retraining, obtaining a loan for the implementation of their own business, relocation of the program participants from the settlements with low potential for social and economic development to the populated areas with high social potential of economic development.

However, this program document can be improved, if an electronic labor exchange is created, as indicated in the President's Letter. Due to digitalization, job opportunities in the field of information technology will increase. This change includes a gradual transformation of the state employment centers. At the same time, the employment centers can be transferred from the state institutions to the enterprises that have the right of economic management. In our opinion, the proposed changes will allow expanding labor market institutions that provide employment, access to citizens and quality improvement through competition.

The proposed initiatives are based on the principles of joint contribution of all labor market participants: state, employers and potential employees, proceeding from the position that each side shall take active measures to ensure employment:

- the state - by creating conditions;
- an employer - by creating workplaces;
- a potential employee - by having a desire to constantly improve his/her competitiveness.

It is also necessary to increase the role of regional executive bodies in addressing youth employment issues, because, with the help of these bodies, the regional employment programs are organized and implemented.

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REFERENCES

Abdiraymova, G.S., Serikzhanova, S.S. (2013). *Professional Choice and Preferences in the Labor Market of Kazakhstan Graduates*. Bulletin of KazNU. Series of Psychology and Sociology.No.2 (45), Almaty. 69-77

Coleman, J. (1990). *Foundations of Social Theory*. Belknap: Harvard University

Press. 27-44. 285

Committee of Statistics of the Republic of Kazakhstan (2017). (access date 14.09.2017). <http://www.stat.gov.kz>

Fursova, V.V., Shakirova, F.Y., Nikitina, T.N., Spirchagova, T.A., MachpalSyzdykova, M.B. (2017). *Employment of University Graduates Across the Post-soviet Space: Problems and Solutions (The Example of Kazakhstan)*. Journal of History Culture and Art Research. Turkey. Copyright Karabuk University. Vol. 6. No. 4. 470-478.

Millerson, G.L. (1964). *The Qualifying Association*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul, 288. Pp.183-185

Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Population of the Republic of Kazakhstan (2017). (access date: 08.10.2017). <https://www.enbek.gov.kz/ru/taxonomy/term/78>.

Parsons, T (1968). *Profession*. Shills D. (ed.). International Encyclopaedia of the Social Science. Macmillan and Free Press. Vol. 12.

Ponomarenko, T.I. (1998). *Installation as a Factor of Forming the Behavior Strategy: Thesis of the Candidate of Psychological Sciences*. Novosibirsk. 6.

Shakirova, A.Y. (2017). *Economic capital of the family as a factor of availability of higher education. A comparative study of universities in Russia and Vietnam*. Hoang Ha Van, Valentina Fursova. QUID-INVESTIGACION..No1. 292-298..

Skuryatipa, E. (2002). *Savings Strategies of the Population: Basic Concepts and Operationalization*. Economic Sociology. Vol. 3.No. 2. 83. Electronic journal. URL: http://vw\v.ecsoc.msses.ru/pdf/ecsoc_t3_n2.pdf/ (access date: 18.09.2017).

Social and Economic Development of the Republic of Kazakhstan. (2017). Vol.1. No. 9. Astana.

Yelzhanova, R.K., Zhumatay, Z.G., Sarzhanizy, A. (2015). *Employment Problems of the University Graduates of Kazakhstan*. Bulletin of KazNTU. No. 3. 522.